

1 July 2009

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Dear Ms. Crain,

Uploaded to NSF Fastlane and attached is the ARCUS Interim Report for Cooperative Agreement ARC-0618885, for the period 1 January 2009 to present. The report describes accomplishments for this time period and includes next steps and action items for each activity. Included in this Interim Report package is:

1. A narrative summary of accomplishments and next steps for each Cooperative Agreement activity;
2. Individual timeline charts for each activity; and
3. Four (4) appendices as supporting materials, as referenced in the narrative.

The programmatic focus in this reporting period was completion of initial planning for the State of the Arctic Conference—we have been very successful in that regard, as we have established the conference dates and location, negotiated a favorable venue contract, announced the meeting to the community, and have established a broad and interdisciplinary conference Organizing Committee. We also have been on-target and successful in many other projects; a few highlights include: completion of the first online issue of *Witness the Arctic*; launching of the 2009 Sea Ice Outlook with the release of the first June Outlook report; successful facilitation of agreement between the SEARCH and ARCSS Committees to move forward in merging of the two programs' science planning structures; and continued implementation of critical activities such as ArcticInfo, website development, and other arctic science planning and education efforts.

The ARCUS Board of Directors and staff are very pleased with the achievements of the past months and the work we have accomplished on behalf of the arctic research community and NSF. We look forward to continuing to work with NSF and the arctic research community on these important initiatives. If you have any questions, please feel free to contact me.

Sincerely,

Helen V. Wiggins
Director of Programs, ARCUS
Principal Investigator, ARCUS Cooperative Agreement

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ARCUS Cooperative Agreement Interim Report Report on Activities for 1 January 2009–Present 1 July 2009

This interim report provides brief updates on the tasks included in the ARCUS CA, ARC-0618885. The narrative text describes activities undertaken from 1 January 2009 to present, and the short-term next steps for each activity.

1.1 SEARCH Coordination

(A. The State of the Arctic Conference is discussed in Section 1.3)

B. Sea Ice Outlook

Continued the Sea Ice Outlook effort, including wrap-up of the 2008 season and launch of the 2009 Sea Ice Outlook. The Sea Ice Outlook website can be found at:

<http://www.arcus.org/search/seaiceoutlook/index.php>.

- i. **Retrospective Working Group Meeting** – A small one-day workshop was held on 10 March 2009 at NSIDC in Boulder, CO, to undertake a retrospective analysis of the 2008 effort and discuss improvements for the 2009 Sea Ice Outlook. The workshop website is at: http://www.arcus.org/search/seaiceoutlook/march_2009_wgm/index.php.

Twenty-seven (27) participants attended the meeting.

- Worked with the Sea Ice Outlook co-chairs (Jim Overland and Hajo Eicken), the Core Integration Group (CIG), and the Advisory Group (AG) to develop the focus and goals for the meeting.
- Developed and maintained the workshop website.
- Worked with J. Overland and H. Eicken to develop the workshop agenda: http://www.arcus.org/search/seaiceoutlook/march_2009_wgm/agenda.php.
- Provided partial venue support (catering costs only; the meeting room was provided by NSIDC).
- Organized meeting room logistics and communicated all logistics information to participants. Participants primarily provided their own travel support; some travel support was provided by NOAA; no participant travel support was provided by ARCUS.
- Supported one (1) Central Office/ARCUS staff (A. Loring) to attend in person; two (2) other ARCUS staff (H. Wiggins and B. Wade) joined via phone.
- Led discussion at the meeting on improvements in SIO format, web delivery, and outreach.
- Posted PowerPoints from the meeting online, with permission from the speakers: http://www.arcus.org/search/seaiceoutlook/march_2009_wgm/agenda.php
- Notes from the meeting are included in Appendix 1.

Next Steps: Working with H. Eicken and J. Overland on the workshop report. Will send draft report to NSF and workshop participants for review. Expect final version

completed in July 2009, with publication as online PDF and limited hardcopies printed in-house.

ii. **Planning and Implementation of the 2009 Sea Ice Outlook**

- Created a Sea Ice Outlook online mailing list to provide a direct means for information dissemination and communication about the SIO. A subscription form is available at: <http://www.arcus.org/search/seaiceoutlook/list.php>. There are currently 102 subscribers to the list.
- Launched the 2009 Sea Ice Outlook with announcements via ArcticInfo and a SIO email list (see latest announcement at: http://siempre.arcus.org/4DACTION/wi_ai_getArcticInfo/4161).
- Completed several website updates and improvements, including: edited and updated content in preparation for the 2009 season, added a “Regional Corner” for regional-scale outlooks (<http://www.arcus.org/search/seaiceoutlook/regional.php>), added a “data links” page (<http://www.arcus.org/search/seaiceoutlook/data.php>), archived the 2008 Outlook material, prepared new templates for the monthly Outlook graphs, and re-organized the directory structure and improved navigation throughout the section.
- Edited and published online the first monthly outlook report, which was released on 24 June 2009. The first 2009 monthly release included a full pan-arctic report and summary (http://www.arcus.org/search/seaiceoutlook/2009_outlook/report_june.php) as well as a regional report (http://www.arcus.org/search/seaiceoutlook/2009_outlook/report_june.php). The June report was announced via ArcticInfo, the SIO website, and other relevant lists. A PDF of the pan-arctic summary report is also attached as Appendix 2.

Next Steps:

Finalize the workshop report (for release July 2009). Add an educational/media resources page to the website (July 2009). Continue to edit, prepare, and release the monthly Outlook reports and write the report summaries; future reports will include a July, August, September, and a “sea ice minimum” report.

C. Develop SEARCH-ARCSS Effort

Continued discussions with the ARCSS Committee and SEARCH regarding the SEARCH-ARCSS merger.

- Held approximately 22 calls and teleconferences with SEARCH representatives and the ARCSS Committee to discuss the ARCSS-SEARCH merge and how to move forward. Worked with ARCSS Committee chair, Josh Schimel, and the ARCSS Committee to create talking points for a meeting in D.C. in early March with J. Schimel, P. Schlosser, and NSF representatives.
- There is agreement with the major parties that the way forward is to hold a small meeting in D.C. with key representatives to discuss a new structure for SEARCH and ARCSS merged programs, and a related science planning structure and process.

- A teleconference will be scheduled for Monday, 13 July to plan for the D.C. meeting (including setting the date and goals). Participants of the teleconference will include ARCUS staff, Peter Schlosser, Josh Schimel, Hajo Eicken, Neil Swanberg (and other NSF staff as appropriate and available), and Matthew Sturm (tentative). ARCUS will develop and distribute teleconference agenda items and discussion topics before the call.
- The SEARCH-ARCSS merge (and the related workshop below, item D) will be coordinated by ARCUS in accordance with best practices of community science planning management and a “competency-driven model” focused on achieving results that all parties define as a success. Metrics of success will be defined beforehand, with defined goals of the SEARCH-ARCSS merge. Throughout the process, the focus will remain on outcomes that result in transformative arctic science. The process will remain transparent and collaborative, with communications to the broader SEARCH and ARCSS communities at key milestones.

Next Steps: Prepare for 13 July teleconference by drafting a call agenda, goals, and objectives for the in-person D.C. meeting.

D. Understanding Change Workshop

- This “Understanding Change” workshop was a recommendation from the last SEARCH SSC meeting, to discuss modeling and analysis research priorities in the context of a merged SEARCH and ARCSS science planning structure.
- Researched possible venues for a workshop, including DC-area, Fairbanks, and Anchorage, AK.
- Planning for the workshop will continue at such time that there is more progress with SEARCH-ARCSS merge; specifically, a tentative “strawperson” model of a merged SEARCH-ARCSS science planning structure and process should be drafted before this workshop is convened. Discussions at the D.C. meeting, above (item C), will include decisions on the timing and focus of this workshop.

Next Steps: Workshop planning will proceed as the SEARCH-ARCSS merge advances.

E. Science Steering Committee (SSC) Meetings

- To save on time, travel, and staff resources and costs, the next SEARCH SSC meeting will be held via electronic means as an eMeeting (using Wimba software). The SEARCH SSC meeting is tentatively set for Wednesday, 19 August. The agenda items will be developed in collaboration with the SEARCH SSC, Panels, and IPMC, but main topics will be follow-up on action items from the last SSC meeting, which include: State of the Arctic Conference planning, Sea Ice Outlook, SEARCH-ARCSS merge, SSC and panel appointments, and other SEARCH business.

Next Steps: Invite SEARCH Panels, IPMC, and other key participants. Draft a tentative eMeeting agenda and circulate it for review.

F. SEARCH Project Catalog

- No activities to report for this period.

Next Steps: No activities planned; minor updates will be completed if required.

G. SEARCH Interagency Meeting

- Discussed with H. Eicken and P. Schlosser regarding a recommendation by the SEARCH Observing Change Panel for an interagency meeting to be held this fall, focused on coordination of arctic observing efforts.

Next Steps: Work with organizers to help plan the meeting in the context of SEARCH goals, perhaps in conjunction with an IARPC principals meeting or the AON PI meeting.

H. AON PI Meeting

- Discussed with H. Eicken and P. Schlosser the initial scope of AON PI meeting in fall and assisted the OCP in drafting a document called “On the implementation of an Arctic Observing Network in the context of SEARCH and other international programs.” Document was sent to NSF by H. Eicken as a discussion document. (Attached as Appendix 3).

Next Steps: Work with organizers to help plan the meeting in the context of SEARCH goals; work with OCP on follow-up items as outlined in Appendix 3.

I. SSC and Panel Support

- Moved forward with nominations of new SSC members, with Hajo Eicken (UAF) as the nominee for next SEARCH SSC Chair, and Uma Bhatt (UAF), Caspar Ammann, (NCAR), and Nate Mantua (U. of Washington) as nominees for SSC Members. Nominees were approved by the IPMC, via N. Swanberg, IPMC Chair.

Next Steps: Work with P. Schlosser to send SSC nominees invitation letters (by end of July 2009). Continue working with OCP and the Understanding Change Panel (UCP) on panel activities. Work with SSC to discuss Responding to Change Panel (RCP) goals and membership this fall.

J. Coordination with Relevant International Efforts

- Discussed with P. Schlosser and M. Fortier creation of draft MOU between ArcticNet and SEARCH to coordinate science and outreach activities (no CA funds would be dedicated through the MOU).

Next Steps: Work with P. Schlosser, M. Fortier, and NSF to draft MOU language to outline coordination activities between SEARCH and ArcticNet. Discuss partnerships with other programs, such as SCANNET, SAON, etc.

K. Other Travel Support for SSC Chair and/or Key SEARCH Representatives

- Supported one (1) trip for P. Schlosser, SEARCH SSC Chair, to the Arctic Science Summit Week (ASSW) in Norway, March 2009 to present and discuss SEARCH activities.

Next Steps: Will process travel support requests; no current travel requests are pending.

L. SEARCH Website

- Completed content updates (e.g., Sea Ice Outlook, meetings, science news, etc.)

Next Steps: Continue website updates, maintenance, and development.

1.2 Arctic Data Coordination

A. GIS of Arctic Observation Activities

- Initiated contract with a consultant and began work to provide core-level metadata for the Geographic Information System (GIS) files of U.S. observing activities that ARCUS created for the U.S. Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee (IARPC) report “Arctic Observing Network (AON): Toward a US Contribution to Pan-Arctic Observing.”

Next Steps: Continue with metadata creation with consultant. Final metadata expected summer 2009. When metadata is completed, GIS layers will be distributed to CADIS, ARMAP, GINA; the availability of the GIS layers will be announced via ArcticInfo and other relevant lists (e.g., SEARCH IPMC, IARPC, etc.).

1.3 State of the Arctic Conference

- Convened an SoA Executive Committee (EC) whose membership includes: Peter Schlosser (SEARCH SSC Chair), Josh Schimel (ARCSS Committee Chair), Maribeth Murray (ISAC Executive Director, member of SEARCH OCP, member of ARCSS Committee), Martin Fortier (ArcticNet Executive Director), Jean-Claude Gascard (DAMOCLES), and Helen Wiggins (ARCUS).

- Researched available venues and dates for conference. Discussions with NSF and the EC resulted in selection of the Hyatt Regency Miami, Miami Convention Center (<http://miamiregency.hyatt.com/hyatt/hotels/index.jsp>) for the week of 15 March 2010.
- Negotiated and finalized contract with venue for meeting rooms and sleeping rooms; completed site visit of venue in June.
- Held four (4) EC planning teleconferences on 23 April, 30 April, 12 May, and 15 June, planning discussions are ongoing via email.
- Created an initial budget for all SoA activities (both 2009 and 2010). Budget was sent to NSF for review.
- Developed and circulated first announcement for meeting (see: http://siempre.arcus.org/4DACTION/wi_ai_getArcticInfo/4180). Announcement was distributed via several listserves, including ArcticInfo, DAMOCLES, ISAC, ArcticNet, IASSA, IASC, and others.
- Worked with the EC on a list of suggestions for the SoA Organizing Committee (OC); OC list was approved by NSF; invitations were sent and nearly all the invitees accepted. The current OC list, in addition to the Executive Committee members, includes: Michael Tjernström (Stockholm U., ISAC), Koji Shimada (Tokyo University of Marine Science and Technology), Hajo Eicken (UAF), Craig Fleener (AK Fish and Game), Max Holmes (Woods Hole Research Center), Bruce Forbes (U. Lapland), Amy Tidwell (UAF), Andi Lloyd (Middlebury College), Jinping Zhao (Ocean U. of China), and Elena Andreeva (Russian Academy of Sciences). Duane Smith (Inuit Circumpolar Council) has tentatively accepted. See Appendix 4.

Next Steps: Work on draft agenda, with initial agenda structure to be completed in July; next Executive Committee teleconference is scheduled for 14 July. Schedule full OC teleconference for July/August. Launch conference website in July. Initial call for community input (ideas for topics and sessions) to be circulated in July.

2.1.1 ARCSS Coordination

A. Merge ARCSS and SEARCH Understanding Change Efforts

See this activity under SEARCH section 1.1.C, above.

B. ARCSS Committee Meetings

- Held three (3) ARCSS Committee (AC) teleconferences, primarily to discuss ARCSS-SEARCH merge, on: 11 February, 25 February, and 14 April 2009. Worked with ARCSS Committee on talking points for J. Schimel to discuss with NSF and P. Schlosser during meeting in DC in early March. Held calls with J. Schimel.

Next Steps: See item 1.1.C, above; will schedule one additional AC teleconference before DC meeting, to gather AC input.

C. HARC Subaward

- Continued subaward with HARC Core Office (with remaining funds from 2008).

Next Steps: Continue subaward; HARC Office planning to deliver HARC Synthesis Report as final product in September 2009.

2.2.1 Bering Sea Research Coordination

A. Joint Science Advisory Board (SAB):

- No activities to report in this period.

Next Steps: Will coordinate and support travel for three (3) BEST PIs to Washington, D.C. for the 2009 meeting of the SAB (dates TBD by the SAB).

B. PI Meeting

- No activities to report in this period.

Next Steps: Will support travel and participation of one (1) ARCUS staff member to the annual PI meeting planned for October 2009 in Girdwood, AK, for meeting and content support.

C. PI teleconferences and eMeetings

- ARCUS staff (A. York) has participated in monthly PI teleconferences to remain abreast of program developments.

Next Steps: ARCUS staff will continue to participate in monthly PI teleconferences.

D. Miscellaneous Travel Support

- Supported travel for two (2) BEST PIs (E. Curchitser, Rutgers University and G. Gibson, UAF) to attend and present at the BEST-BSIERP Modeling Workshop in June 2009 in Seattle, Washington.

Next Steps: Provide travel support to address program goals.

E. Development of an Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Plan for Beaufort and Chukchi Seas

- ARCUS staff served on the organizing committee for the Arctic Research and Monitoring Workshop held 23 January 2009 in conjunction with the Alaska Marine Science Symposium. One (1) ARCUS Staff (A. York) attended the workshop. No workshop participant travel or logistics support was provided by ARCUS. This workshop was an initial step toward development of a comprehensive monitoring and assessment plan.

- The report from the workshop, *Arctic Research and Monitoring Workshop: Toward a Strategy for the Chukchi and Beaufort Seas*, has undergone public review (with editing and content input from ARCUS) and was released on 1 June (see ArcticInfo announcement at: <http://siempre.arcus.org/4DACTION/wi ai getArcticInfo/4177>).

Next Steps: All planned activities completed; no additional activities expected.

F. HBEST Science Plan

- No activities to report in this period.

Next Steps: Final editing, publication, and distribution in fall 2009 of the HBEST (Humans-BEST) Science Plan “Sustaining the Bering Sea Ecosystem: A Social Sciences Research Plan.”

2.4.1 Arctic Section Science Materials

A. Update the Arctic Discoveries Poster

- No activities to report in this period.

Next Steps: Work with NSF to update the *Arctic Discoveries* poster for use as an NSF outreach tool; aim for completion in summer.

3.1 Arctic Science Education Activities

A. Provide Support for One (1) Science Teacher to Attend PolarTREC Orientation

- No activities to report in this period – this activity was not required as the selected teacher was unable to attend PolarTREC Orientation nor participate in an expedition.

B. Outdoor Days at UAF

- Participated in “Outdoor Days,” a three-day outdoor education program held 12–14 May for 6th graders, sponsored by the U.S. Fish & Wildlife Service and held annually in Fairbanks, AK. ARCUS hosted a “Climate Change in the Arctic” Earth Sciences station. The activity introduced students to carbon and the carbon cycle. Students were introduced to a variety of careers in climate change, and developed ideas for reducing their own carbon footprint. 630 students from 12 different schools attended, along with parents and teachers.

Next Steps: All planned activities completed; no additional activities expected.

C. Other science education activities

- No other science education activities to report for this time period.

Next Steps: Work with program officer to manage, or participate in, arctic science education activities, as opportunities arise, including an eMeeting this summer focused on sharing information about products that emerged (or will emerge) from IPY education efforts.

3.2 Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series

- Supported one (1) AVS speaker this period, Michelle Ridgway, who visited the Alaska SeaLife Center in Seward (see: http://www.arcus.org/arctic_speaker/2009_tours.html). Updated AVS webpages.

Next Steps: Continue current program, with support for AVS tours as applications are received.

4.1 Witness the Arctic Newsletter

- Completed, published, and distributed 15,000 copies of Witness (Winter 2008/2009, Volume 13, Number 1) in March 2009. This issue is a 24-page newsletter with a feature story by Mark Serreze of the National Snow and Ice Data Center.
- Published the online PDF version of the newsletter on ARCUS' website (http://www.arcus.org/witness_the_arctic/winter_08_09/index.html).
- Solicited and edited contributions for the Spring 2009 issue of Witness (Volume 13, Number 2). The feature story, authored by Mead Treadwell, highlighted the increased visibility brought to arctic issues by the accomplishments of the recently completed International Polar Year.
- Created online webpages for the new online format.
- Completed and released online issue on 29 May; the issue is available at: http://www.arcus.org/witness_the_arctic/spring_09/index.html

Next Steps: Solicit and edit contributions for September 2009 issue, and prepare database-driven searchable interface for future online issues.

4.2 Website and Internet Resources

- Continued to update website, develop new content, and improve functionality. Increasingly used website-tracking software to analyze website use patterns, using Google analytics.

Next Steps: Continue website updates and developments, with a specific focus on direct program needs.

4.3 ArcticInfo Mailing List

- Continued to develop and maintain the moderated mailing list, including receiving, editing, and posting announcements to the list. Through this reporting period, edited and posted an average of two (2) announcements per day.

Next Steps: Continue to manage the ArcticInfo listserv.

4.4 Directory of Arctic Researchers

- Continued to develop and maintain the Directory of Arctic Researchers, which currently contains 4,129 individual entries. Held small staff meeting to establish a more efficient process of updating the Directory.

Next Steps: Beginning in July, contact researchers in the Directory to update their research expertise and contact information; by end of summer, will send out an ArcticInfo to invite new researchers to join the Directory.

4.5 Internet Media Archive (IMA)

- Continued to develop and maintain the IMA and work on the backlog of resources waiting to be entered into the IMA database:
 - Added 23 presentation/talk videos from various science workshops.
 - Made 968 photos publicly available.

Next Steps: Continue to develop and maintain the IMA; organize 2–3 “special collections” with commonly used sets of media (e.g., select photos of arctic landscapes, videos from meeting talks).

4.6 Arctic Community Outreach

A. Arctic Community Meeting Space at AGU Fall Meeting

- No activities to report this period.

Next Steps: Begin planning for the community meeting space in early fall, or when AGU and hotel organization allows.

B. Arctic Forum 2008 Proceedings

- Finalized and printed proceedings of the *Arctic Forum 2008*, “Tipping Points—The Arctic and Global Change.” The proceedings include presentation and poster abstracts,

and summaries of panel, participant, and student discussions on priorities in arctic science and education. The volume was announced on 19 June, and is available via hardcopy by request and online at:

http://www.arcus.org/annual_meetings/arctic_forum_archive/2008/index.html.

Hardcopies were sent to AF participants and other key members of the community.

Next Steps: Respond to hardcopy requests, as received.

C. Other Community Outreach

- No other community outreach activities to report for this period.

Next Steps: Will participate in outreach at AGU and other prominent arctic or related meetings and conferences, as appropriate.

5.1 Core Support

- Continued support of direct activities that address multiple tasks and programs, including portions of the Executive Director, Director of Programs, and System Administrator salaries.

Next Steps: Continue Core Support of CA activities; staff time, however, will be allocated to direct projects as much as possible.

ARCUS Year 2 CA Timeline (1 January–31 December 2009)

1. ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING

1.3 State of the Arctic Conference

ARCUS Year 2 CA Timeline (1 January–31 December 2009)

2. NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION

2.1 ARCSS Program Coordination

ARCUS Year 2 CA Timeline (1 January–31 December 2009)

2. NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION *(Continued)*

2.2.1 Arctic Natural Sciences Program Coordination: Bering Sea Research Coordination

HBEST Science Plan: Final Editing, Publication, and Distribution

Participation in monthly PI teleconferences, eMeetings if needed

2.4.1 Arctic Section Science Materials

Update the *Arctic Science Discoveries* Poster

ARCUS Year 2 CA Timeline (1 January–31 December 2009)

3. ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION

3.1 Arctic Science Education Activities

JAN	FEB	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUG	SEPT	OCT	NOV	DEC
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Participation in "Outdoor Days" (12-14 May)

Arctic science education and outreach activities, to be determined with the program officer as opportunities arise.

3.2 Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series

Ongoing Tour Management (6 Tours)

ARCUS Year 2 CA Timeline (1 January–31 December 2009)

4. INFORMATION AND OUTREACH

5. CORE SUPPORT

Appendix 1. Notes from the Sea Ice Outlook Workshop

Sea Ice Outlook Workshop
10 March 2009
National Snow and Ice Data Center (NSIDC)
Building RL-2, Room 155/153
Boulder, Colorado

Meeting Notes from Sea Ice Outlook Central Office

Introduction

A Sea Ice Outlook (SIO) Workshop was held in Boulder, Colorado, at the National Snow and Ice Data Center (NSIDC), 10 March 2009, to discuss lessons learned from the 2008 SIO and to plan for the 2009 SIO. Participants included representatives from the SIO Core Integration and Advisory Groups, 2008 SIO Contributors, Central Office Staff, and others. The morning session was dedicated to presentations on Outlook methods, and the afternoon session focused on group discussion of scientific goals, content, format, and presentation, focused on planning for the 2009 Outlook.

The agenda, presentations, and the participant list are all available via the workshop website at: http://www.arcus.org/search/seaiiceoutlook/march_2009_wgm/index.php

Detailed notes and action items from the afternoon discussion session, grouped by topics, follow.

Scientific Goals and Content

The 2008 Outlook was considered a success as a tool for synthesizing and communicating where the scientific community stands as far as understanding seasonal and interannual variability of arctic sea ice. The Outlook was utilized and followed by the arctic science community, as well as the media and public.

What is the Purpose of the Outlook?

Participants discussed the purpose of the Outlook from two points of view: that of the science community and that of the public. There was general consensus that the term "Outlook" is still the best name, but that there seems to be some confusion about the purpose. Participants agreed that the purpose of the outlook needs to be more clearly defined as a research activity (not a prediction exercise). The caveats from last year need to remain the same, but should be more articulately stated. The new description of the SIO must also clearly indicate that the outlook number is the monthly mean—not the actual minimum. Participants also agreed that it would be useful to highlight particular regions, and include an uncertainty range. Detailed comments are below.

- Jim—really impressed with all comments from this a.m. A lot of ideas sprouted from going through the process, and from building on practices of last year. Stay fairly close to purpose and procedure of last year w/ regard to exchange w/in community. If it's not broken, don't fix it. Good model on the scientific exchange. Don't get overly anxious

about forecast / product part. Think about it as a further goal. But, have same caveats as we did last year. Primarily a community among ourselves. Having said that, there is a broader interest in the product. So, maybe have a shell that is the same as last year for scientific community, but think more in terms of additional outreach activities. Rather than just a black and white forecast, a lot of people really liked having ability to see everyone's input verbatim – seeing some of the process was valuable.

- Todd—Bulletin Board—have all data in one place so everyone is essentially starting in the same place. Look at state of Arctic from all those sources.
- Walt—in terms of data, long term there will always be glitches, but you can account for those—have to be patient in getting the data, and taking more time to evaluate. Don't think we'll get to the point that we'll have errors and can't do anything about it
 - If all info is available, individuals can make choices. Find way to make really easily accessible
 - Public doesn't like when #s change b/c they get very suspicious.
 - Ron—I don't like idea of it being so public.
 - Jim—two levels of simplification for public. On one level, scientists want to live with the ambiguity, but we have to find a way to talk to public
 - Pablo—different access to public?
 - Jim—no, different levels of synthesis
 - Serreze—"real" science watered down
 - Add a "Joe the plumber" level"?
 - For now, hide behind the disclaimer and not worry about public
 - Hajo—NSIDC still provides "historical data" and shows the "real" stuff
 - Jim—for scientists, we're saying, "this is the reference point" that we're going to use.
 - Can be useful to have different numbers / reference different numbers
 - You have to be careful what you put out, so you don't get burned
 - Jim Maslanik—people will always find something to burn you with
- We need to be really clear that this is A RESEARCH ACTIVITY
 - Weislaw—are we trying to satisfy public? Or trying to improve our science? We need to really define what we're doing, b/c they are two different things.
 - We need to do both
 - Be really clear where numbers are coming from
 - Jamie—Nobody computing ice extent from AMSR data?
 - Walt—No, but it's based off a different algorithm, so consistency isn't there.
 - Jamie—seems like it would be educational to plot two lines—from different data. The way to resolve the difference between those is to take a look at both.
 - Walt—maybe that's not a bad way to do it, to give people an uncertainty range
 - Pablo—IMS Snow and Ice Product, would like to develop into something similar to sea ice index, to compare the two, cross-validation.
 - Hajo—NSIDC gives a single number. So, maybe discussing uncertainty is valuable (guy from Jacksa will be providing data this year?)
 - There will be some ways for people to do that if they really want to dig into it.
 - SIO doesn't want to compete with what NSIDC is already doing very well.

- Walt—focus should really be on the science, what can we learn from it. BUT, we are doing it on a public website, and so we need to be aware of that.
- Pablo—we have to start thinking about better resolution systems to capture the real extent. Need to look regionally.
 - Walt—maybe the way to do it
- Florence—presenting anomalies v. presenting actual numbers
- Weislaw—Are the two passages open at the same time or not?
 - Issue with regionality
 - But still a need for a number
- Hajo—We should draw the conclusion that "here's the area where there's general consensus" but at the same time, we'll see areas where there is disagreement, which may have to do with methods (guidance) others might just be on principle.
 - Highlight those two areas at the end of the season?
 - Jim—for scientists we need to make a guideline (Sept. average minimum, related to NSIDC #) Need to have a common theme. Second point is that we need to have the website for all the links of various data. As a scientific problem, there is inter-comparison
- Pablo—what we're looking for is a mean minimum? There is and continues to be some confusion. So, we need to really define what we are shooting for. ACTUAL minimum or monthly mean?
 - Serrze—monthly
- Does the term "Outlook" still work?—consensus, yes.

ACTION ITEM:

- **Jim, Hajo, and the Central Office to work with core group to develop a clearer explanation of the purpose of the SIO.**
- **Need to be clear about what the SIO values represent. Participants agreed on values to represent the monthly average minimum.**

How do we summarize and synthesize our results for the public?

Participants discussed ways to make the 2009 Outlook more understandable for the public, but maintain the focus as a research activity. The summary needs to provide additional information (not just simplification) (i.e., why was one number really low and others were really high?). Participants would be asked to provide a little more information about their data and outlooks. The idea would be to provide the public with a greater understanding of the activity. Detailed comments are below.

- Jamie—I wouldn't try to make this too simple. But don't over simplify. It's good for people to have something that's a little more complicated, especially if we have a good explanation.
- The "One Paragraph" "Executive Summary" needs to be clearer. Additional information, not further simplification. I.E., why was one of the number really low, and others were really high? Make those kinds of discrepancies really clear.
- Highlighting discrepancies to look at. V. this is just uncertainty and we have to live with it.
- "simplification" is the wrong term. Help people UNDERSTAND.

- Looking at the same format, but more value added interpretation.—Why were there winners and losers?
- Jim—action item, talk to Carlson, what would it take to have more value added. Secondary users are asking more interpretation.
- Kyle—ask people to talk about their data a little more. "This is my number, this is why it's outside of what we see because X"
- Ignatius—Who knows who's method is right.
- Walt—The science can come out of comparing the different methods, whose is working and why? "Cone of uncertainty" – so you have individual cones of uncertainty, and then a combined.
 - We were on the low end of this because xyz, each group could provide own assessment.
- More interpretation, and not just simple facts. But we'll keep in mind we're not talking about "winners" and "losers"

ACTION ITEMS:

- **Jim will talk to Dave Carlson for ideas about more public-level information**
- **Central Office to outline ideas for public-level information**

Measures of Uncertainty

Participants discussed the value of including an uncertainty range in the Outlook. The idea was met with both enthusiasm and apathy, but it was decided that mentioning some kind of bounding (like a range) would help to clarify the Outlook as a whole. Importantly, emphasis should be placed on the nature of the exercise and the motivation behind it. One idea was to point out that more mature forecast efforts demonstrate predictive skill, which this group has not done. But, if we think about it similarly to how hurricane paths are forecasted, people may have more of an understanding—in the same way that people understand that hurricane predictions are not 100% accurate, so should they understand that the SIO is not a predictive activity (think about how the path of a hurricane is demonstrated visually—as the time scale gets longer, the path of the hurricane is shown in a large cone, indicating its exact location to be unpredictable). In thinking about uncertainty, it is important to think about where this activity will go in the future. Perhaps we can aim for a more systematic evaluation of the product in 2010. Would there be any value in an outside reviewer looking at the process and the product(s)? Perhaps after this season, we can have a meeting with an outside examiner, and then set up a formal evaluation technique for the 2010 season. Detailed comments are below.

- "Emphasize the preliminary nature of the exercise and the purpose of motivating our own community to pursue short term forecasts. Point out that more mature forecast efforts demonstrate predictive skill, which we have not done yet. Point the media to examples of what we are trying to achieve in the long run"
 - Really need to show the RANGE. If you just pick a number, then the public really gets the wrong idea.
- Walt—think about a way to combine in a reasonable way. Think about it in the hurricane forecast way. People understand that hurricane forecasts are not really accurate, and we need to get that same message across here.
- Kyle—as long as there is SOME kind of bound, we can have a better understanding.

- Ice Center had range
- Jim—Do we really want to move to more systematic evaluation of the product (2010).
 - 2nd year we have the same goal as first year, so building on first year, but then think forward to 2010 to something more "product" like
 - "We practiced for 2 years, now maybe lets have more formal process"
 - Are we heading toward a formal evaluation process?
- Pablo—Can we actually forecast where is going to be open and where is the ice going to be? That seems like what would be really useful.
- Hajo—If you give us a number, identify what the uncertainty is (if you want / are able to)—encourage, but not require?
- Would it be useful to have an outsider come in and say X method works better b/c blah blah ...?
 - Ron—Do the community provided predictions give enough info to demonstrate predictive skill?
 - Jim M—are we asking ourselves to do something that other disciplines do? Use multiple feeds? Do we HAVE to say this method is the "best" method?
 - Serreze—weather forecasting, use many different feeds, knowing that they are all "wrong" and then fit them to make sense.
 - Jim—I don't think we're going toward one method, but we're learning how to do it, we're developing our predictive skill, still don't really know what we're doing.
 - Ron—are we too hung up on ice extent?
 - Pablo—again, a spatial distribution of different ice types is what "we" would like."
- Hajo—subgroups may be interested in going in particular direction, but community as whole may be more interested in looking at all variability. Maybe invite an outside reviewer to look at it, just to get some ideas in there that we haven't necessarily thought about. Value in that?
- Ignatius—how do ENSO do it?
 - Jamie—comparisons with ocean temps, etc.
- Jim—continue where we are this summer, and then following year, double track, continue on the way we are, and then another where we do more of a prediction track.
 - Next fall, have a meeting, have some outsider take a look (Calder to support?)
 - Then 2010 set up a formal evaluation technique.
- Jamie—so few degrees of freedom
 - Frank—Use hindcast mode to give more than 2 years

ACTION ITEM:

- **In the solicitation for outlooks, include a call for uncertainty ranges (not mandatory)**
- **Core group to determine how we display and communicate the uncertainty ranges**

Regional Outlooks

Workshop participants discussed the overall value to regional outlooks and decided that they were important enough to keep in the Outlook. Some discussion focused on dividing the Arctic into regions or “sectors” in order to better anticipate what might happen overall. In this division, it would be useful to find a standardized way of expressing anticipated ice conditions (like a

stop-light, for instance: red (less than average amount of ice), yellow (average amount of ice), green (more than average amount of ice), etc.). Participants determined it would be useful to separate the regional outlooks from the whole, and have a "regional corner" where regional outlooks are highlighted. Detailed comments are below.

- Hajo—regional outlooks useful, anticipate what is likely to happen, local coastal communities are more interested in this. But, is there value in the small outlooks to the overall Outlook?
 - Serreze—yes, definitely, think about what the Coast Guard would want
 - Ron—divide whole into sectors, we could be really successful in anticipating what will happen. I think that the central arctic is going to be the most difficult this year. Will there be ice in x area at summer minimum? Yes or no? Some simple code: 0, 1, 2 (red, yellow, green)
 - Probability map in quadrants, sectors, etc.
 - Diane—coast guard is already kind of doing it—this is the direction that people are eventually thinking
 - It's not so much what is the ice, it's WHEN will the ice be there?
 - Jamie—maybe that's the key—determination of things that go into it
 - Are you doing observations based on last year, or on something else? Multi-year fraction in the fall, or???
- Hajo—find a way to express anticipated ice conditions, divide into sectors, but then we need a bit more guidance about what kind of information is NEEDED?
 - Jim M— Can be a building block as to how this might pan out? Just a couple sentences or a paragraph? Cant' put numbers necessarily ...
 - Yes, that would be a good start.
 - ACTION—solicit paragraph on ice conditions on certain sector and forward to NIC for analyzing
- Jim—Regional basis may be harder for predictability, because it's more affected by weather.—don't want EVERYONE to do a sector-based approach. On the other hand, there is a real need for passing info, and real-time observations. So, want to know overall ice extent, but then want to have a regional corner, that we can further highlight. Think about how we expand the regional part without changing the main outlook.

ACTION ITEMS:

- **Hajo work up protocol of how to deal with regional outlook content**
- **Solicit paragraph on ice conditions in certain sectors and forward to NIC for analyzing**

Making SIO Data Available via the Website

The suggestion was made that it would help to clarify the discrepancies in the individual outlooks if people had access to data used to create the Outlooks and showing initial conditions. The website should include a section of relevant data sets, and could include a closed section where people could contribute their initial data. The group reached a consensus on sharing data—it would be useful to know everyone's starting point. Some participants would only feel comfortable providing data to individuals (not to have posted online).

- Jim—is there some very preliminary info that Ron could provide by May?
 - Ron—takes a while Maybe get some preliminary
- Serrezze—Jim M, tracking data?
- Jim—it would be good for people to provide info
- Ron—I can provide preliminary info, but don't want it to be on web, need to provide to individuals.
- Jim—Ideally, it would be good to know what initial conditions people are starting from. Share to be as a source of info for a lot of people to see.
- Hajo—could have section in relevant links / data sets where we separate out data people are using to initiate their outlook (ASMR, NSIDC, plus YOURS)
- Jim—science community would be really interested in initial conditions. And how we as a community can do better.
- Jamie—other field observations that if they were made in spring would help? Snow? Buoys? Ice-mass balance? Drift history?
 - Ignatius—could make it available. Available already?
 - Hajo to talk to Don
 - Jamie—seems like in long run, would be nice to have some kind of campaign, (LONG TERM) if we want to do this in organized way in long term, short of some giant program, could we do some kind of observational data?
 - Pablo—one in March / April
 - Coast guard
 - Ron—NASA p3 – transit from barrow to Fairbanks and back

ACTION ITEMS:

- **Initial data will be solicited, with a deadline of 15 May 2009**
- **Hajo will talk to Don Perovich (who was absent from the meeting) about getting his buoy data for users (this information will be added to the "initial data")**
- **Central Office will create a section of website to include resources / links to data showing initial conditions and / or related data**

SIO Format and Presentation

Layout of SIO Graph(s)

Discussion focused primarily on the need to make the visual depiction of the outlook values more appealing and easier to understand. Some suggestions included naming the individuals in each bar, including an uncertainty range, and color-coding the bars by "type" of outlook (i.e., method).

- Serrezze—didn't like graph, list who it is in each bar
 - Can then include uncertainties
 - Group different types of forecasts (models, statistical, ensemble, etc)
 - Graphics can convey a lot of info if they are done well
 - Color code bars by type
- Jim—Responses should be anonymous so you're not swayed by
 - Do we do something different for scientists v. public?

- Walt—labels on bars, can still do something along the same lines so you can have cumulative look
 - Weighted?
 - NOT have a single average ensemble value?
- Walt—median, and then range of observations / outlooks?
- Hajo—Produce "alternative" plots to send to review committee?
 - Concern about having a single number that people will focus on.
 - The idea of the graphic visualization needs to be further thought out, discussed
 - Median would go in middle in Serreze's idea
- Walt—plot in terms of conveying—see how forecast evolves over time, on one graph? Finding a way to see that change graphically.
- Jim—if there are easy analyses that people would like done, we can certainly add to them, but not sure we want to add to

ACTION ITEMS:

- **Central Office to use last year's data to come up with examples of graph types we could use**
- **Then core group and Central Office to discuss and finalize graphs**

Additions and Changes to Website

Participants discussed the value of adding another section to the website that would include links to outside resources, information on how people determine their outlook number, a short summary of winter / spring conditions, and an entire tab dedicated to specific regions (e.g., “The Regional Corner”).

- Another link or something on the side, as to how people are coming up with the number or definition of ice extent.
- Glossary of different terms, including the different definitions
 - Link to the NSIDC glossary site
- Short summary of winter / spring conditions
 - People making available data that assessments are based on —esp. with regional corner
 - NIC—narrative of what winter / summer / spring conditions are like?
 - Walt—NSIDC has a general idea
 - Jim—want to encourage as many resources that are primary links, we may abstract some of it, but the idea is that it would be good to have reviews, maybe pull some together.

ACTION ITEM:

- **Central Office will work on various additions to the website, and circulate among core group (including data, regional corner, etc).**

Timing and Naming of Reports

Last year's outlook produced some confusion with the naming convention. A decision was made to have outlook titles based on the month they are released, but with the caveat that it is based on the prior month's data.

- Todd—Outlook 1, Outlook 2
- If it comes out in July, say "July Report: Based on conditions in June"
- Turn around?
 - Shorten the review process—one review period instead of 2.
 - Would shorten by about 5 days
 - Raises the question about revising committees (cig / ag)
 - Have a smaller core committee?? That is part of initial review committee?
 - No objections
- Jim / Hajo—after workshop, discussed that could rearrange core group to be a smaller "editorial board" (would include Jim, Hajo, Walt, and possibly Ceci Bitz). Other core group members could be shifted to the advisory group.

ACTION ITEMS:

- **Name reports for the month they come out**
- **Further discuss best ways to shorten the review process, including one review from groups rather than two, shorten time for review period, etc.**

Process / Timing for Soliciting Outlooks

A broad solicitation for initial data / spring conditions will be issued in early April, with a data input deadline of 15 May. The first outlook would be due at the end of May for a release in early June. The "initial data" would then be placed in the data section of the website, with an explanation of what it is, and how it might be useful.

- Have broad announcement in early April for solicitation, Data input through May 15, and then 1st outlooks (based on May data) will be due May 30th; and same goes for identifying links, would want website up no later than mid-May

ACTION ITEMS:

- **Immediately begin website additions and changes, as well as outline of regional corner, etc.**
- **Solicitation for initial data - solicitation for links to "initial SIO data" to be done in April—deadline 15 May**
- **Solicitation for individual Outlooks – should do late April, deadline for outlooks end of May, for an early June release**

Products, Papers, Outreach

The original aim to publish 2008 results was to produce a paper for *EOS*, but that will not work, for reasons explained by Jim (see details below). However, *EOS* does have an "announcements" section that the SIO may be able to take advantage of for further publicity. Hajo asked the group to start thinking about products for this year's SIO—possibly a poster or oral session at AGU, a group paper to be submitted to a peer-reviewed journal, possibly several white papers (to be

worked on jointly at a paper-writing meeting), also with communication to funding agencies. The group was asked to think about this for further discussion at the end of the season. Detailed comments are below.

- Status on EOS? —funny but tragic story (Jim)—EOS now you have to write a proposal, sent in at beg of Nov. Finally heard back last week (on proposal!) They said “We don't need another Sea Ice is Going Away article.” But, they do have brief announcements. So, to that, send in what we're doing this year, as well as what happened last year. Talk about communication effort. Focus on ongoing product.
- Hajo—people are putting in time and effort, at some point we may want to split into "volunteer fire crew" and the "professionals" maybe in form of session at a meeting, a small paper that summarizes "this is where we are" and "this is where it could go." Asks group to think about this. (paper writing meeting)
 - EOS, maybe they'll give an advertisement
 - Advertise link to broader community
 - People participate b/c they get something out of it. How much more do we want to have? (how much more than website and communication)
 - Talks about doing joint papers on what happened in 2007, idea is to get whole community working together
 - But don't want to say that collective is better than smaller individually organized working groups
 - Spending more time on methods (for next winter)
 - Try for something at AGU?
 - Rather have individuals get rewarded than us try to do some collective group thing
 - More relevant to bring together different perspectives, aim for group paper? Small group paper?
 - Poster session at AGU? May not get an oral session
 - NASA is under conference travel restrictions, so keep in mind
 - Joint session at AGU / atmospheric forecasting? Get ideas from different community that knows things we don't
 - Jim—conclusion—what is way forward? Are we going to do a white paper? Or are we going to go toward individual contributions?
 - HAJO—need to have something that we can pass on to funding agencies. Here are areas that appear to be promising, or areas that are needed, etc.
 - Would we put this on the website? Make it transparent? (YES!)
 - Does it have to be peer reviewed or not?
 - Will be internationally important, as well.
 - Helen—we could also add a simple webpage that has a bibliography of relevant peer-reviewed papers.

ACTION ITEM:

- **Jim to look into making use of the "announcements" section of EOS**
- **Discussion of products (presentations, papers, etc.) to be further discussed further and at end of season**

Media and Public Outreach

A major point of discussions at this workshop was to make the purpose and content of the SIO more understandable to the public. All participants emphasized, however, that in doing this, the public **MUST** understand that the activity is **NOT** a formal forecast. One suggestion was to have a press release at the beginning of the season to get the press's attention—to give them something to "track" and then write about at the end of the season. It is crucial that this is cast as an **initial** outcast, and not a formal forecast. Another discussion point was a resource for K-12 teachers—links and resources. ARCUS can develop this.

- Walt—NSIDC only does a press release at the end, intentionally
- Jim—Maybe have one for June outlook based on May data?
 - Walt—press releases get attention. That will raise the visibility in terms of public. Would want to have some sort of "canned response" or at least someone responsible for responses (ARCUS, NOAA research, or someone)
 - Plan is to come out of our shell a bit more? If so, implies that we need to do something a bit more. Write in a way that science journalists will pick up on to track Really cast it as "initial" "outlook" "scientists coming together to share data" etc.
 - Pick up idea of press conference at AGU at end of season
- K-12 / teacher resources?
 - Best done through links
 - Resource not curriculum
 - Solicit for potential educational reference

ACTION ITEMS:

- **Central office will draft a press release for beginning of season and then pass around to core group**
- **Central Office will work on K-12 links / resources**

Miscellaneous

The addition of more links to press/media stories and the SIO email list will be really valuable changes to this year's Outlook. It would also be useful to have a set of stock SIO slides that could be downloaded for presentations.

- Debriefing / post-mortem after each season really valuable.
 - Good to have as a formal jumping off point. Make this part of AGU / summarizing / Workshop type of thing / web-meeting
- Teleconference?
 - Would rather have people spending time thinking about what their number is and why, than to spend time holding conference calls, etc.
- Mailing List will be valuable
- Serreze—few stock ppt slides on SIO

ACTION ITEMS:

- **Central Office to create a set of stock PPT slides about the SIO**
- **Develop a plan for a post-mortem meeting or in person meeting**
- **Encourage use of SIO email list for group communication**

Sea Ice Outlook | 2009 Outlook

September Sea Ice Outlook: June Report

Report Released: 24 June 2009

SUMMARY

The outlook for arctic sea ice for September 2009, based on May data, indicates a continuation of low pan-arctic sea ice extent and no indication that a return to historical levels will occur. The June Sea Ice Outlook Report is based on a synthesis of 15 individual pan-arctic estimates (plus six regional contributions) utilizing a range of methods; two additional pan-arctic contributions provide background information on recent sea ice observations.

The June Outlook indicates a similar, or slightly increased, extent compared to the 2008 value of 4.7 million square kilometers. However, there is a small but important probability of a major sea ice loss event this year, given that the ice is thinner and younger than previous years, combined with a possibility of atmospheric conditions that cause significant ice retreat.

Refer to Figure 1 on page 2 of this document.

The range of individual outlook values is from 4.2 to 5.0 million square kilometers. All estimates are well below the 1979–2007 September climatological mean value of 6.7 million square kilometers. Half of the responses are in the range of 4.9–5.0 million square kilometers; the remaining estimates are in the range of 4.2–4.7 (Figure 1, above). The uncertainty / error values, from those groups that provided them, are close to 0.5 million square kilometers, thus many of the values overlap.

Interestingly, the outlook values for the June Report were in fairly close agreement and the range of estimates was much lower than in 2008. This is likely the result of improved and more consistent approaches in the individual outlooks, as the community has applied the insights and lessons learned regarding oceanic and meteorological factors from the 2008 Outlook effort.

More details about the pan-arctic outlooks, including the individual outlooks, can be found in the full report.

Regional outlooks can be found in the [Regional Corner](#).

September 2009 Sea Ice Outlook: June Report*

*Report based on May 2009 data

Appendix 3. AON Implementation Document

On the implementation of an Arctic Observing Network in the context of SEARCH and other international programs

12 June 2009

Background

Implementation of an Arctic Observing Network (AON) that addresses the broad set of questions identified in the SEARCH Science Plan and the recommendations from the SEARCH Implementation Workshop (SIW) requires planning, coordination and analysis of data and model output over a range of disciplines and scales. At present, a number of national and international observing efforts are underway in the Arctic, with three programs of particular relevance: the SEARCH AON, the European DAMOCLES program (which is winding down but is spawning sustained observing efforts) and the Canadian ArcticNet Program. With US national agencies and others maintaining observation efforts in the Arctic, there is an urgent need for coordination, consolidation and optimization of the existing observing system elements, as well as for development of a strategy for enhancing and sustaining the observing system.

Arctic Observing System Design Considerations

From the perspective of SEARCH and its observing component, the US AON, a number of issues arise that need to be considered by individual researchers, the community involved in the implementation of the observing system, and funding agencies who support the system.

- (i) **Guidance by science questions:** The observing system has to be guided by the science questions that underpin the Arctic environmental change programs (SEARCH for the U.S. and ISAC as the emerging international umbrella). These science questions have matured during the past years and are captured in the several science plans, most recently in the ISAC science plan.
- (ii) ***Comprehensive nature of observing effort:*** The broad range of questions and disciplines that are part of the observing system presents a challenge to traditional approaches in designing and maintaining an appropriately balanced observing system (e.g., remote sensing vs. ground-based, surveys vs. point-based measurements, broad regions of interest).
- (iii) ***Coordination of measurement activities:*** Individual projects derive guidance on specifics of measurement activities from broader program plans and project goals, but intercomparability and thematic compatibility of data sets require additional efforts in determining sampling rates, spatial resolution of measurements, site selection, and variables to be measured. International coordination, for example through initiatives such as the International Study of Arctic Change (ISAC) can help maximize synergy, e.g., through joint workshops or meetings on a regular (biennial?) schedule.

- (iv) *Need for observing system to be highly adaptive:* The rate of change in the Arctic, in particular in relation to standard funding cycles or the response times of international research organizations and programs, requires new approaches in the design and optimization of an observing system. The complexity of the problem, the fast pace of change and the importance of observing the anthrosphere in the context of SEARCH require that the observing system be highly adaptive, allowing for the system to evolve on the timescales required to track rapid change and plan for effective response. Abrupt changes that have to be expected in the transition of the Arctic into a new state pose challenges for the observing system, specifically concerning its capacity for high sampling rates.
- (v) *Dual purpose of AON:* SEARCH explicitly identified the need for an Arctic observing system to serve the scientific community (informed by the SEARCH science questions as outlined in the SEARCH science plan and SIW report) as well as serving information needs of key stakeholder groups. This duality of purpose requires novel approaches with respect to the design of an observing network.
- (vi) *Multi-disciplinary nature of an observing system:* As outlined in SEARCH planning documents, the interdisciplinary nature of many of the pressing SEARCH science questions and societal needs require a multi-disciplinary observing network with a degree of disciplinary intertwining and topical breadth that is pioneering at this scale. At present, funded AON projects (from CADIS web site, retrieved 24 April 2009) comprise the following topical areas: atmosphere (7), ocean and sea ice (18), hydrology and cryosphere (6), terrestrial ecosystems (3), human dimensions (1), data management and coordination (2). The current portfolio may change as the program evolves, and may require guidance to ensure the disciplinary balance needed to meet the overarching scientific goals of the program. At the same time, the concentration of atmosphere-ocean-sea ice projects reflects critical information needs and scientific opportunities.

Observing System Design Considerations

Ideally, one would like to base the design and implementation of a complex observing system on a comprehensive theoretical framework with the following attributes:

- (a) Capability to optimize distribution and mix of sensors for the set of variables that are identified by interpretation of existing data through synthesis, modeling and scale analyses.
- (b) Exploration of tradeoffs between deployment of sensors for specific variables within and across domains with respect to loss of knowledge (including information needs by stakeholders outside of the scientific community) that can be derived from the data stream coming off the observing system.
- (c) Examination of irreversible loss of information on the Arctic system dynamics through termination or re-location of time series measurements.
- (d) Determination of accuracy at which variables have to be measured to yield the information needed for answering the science questions underpinning the observing system.

Unfortunately, such theoretical frameworks are currently not available and will not be available for the foreseeable future because they depend on the capability to describe the dynamics of the integrated Arctic system in a 4-dimensional fashion. De facto, a fully coupled, multi-domain Arctic system model is needed as the starting point for such a theoretical approach to an observing system design. In the absence of such a tool, a more pragmatic and empirically based approach has to be followed to maximize the return from investments into system-scale, integrated, long-term observing systems.

Empirical Approach to Arctic Observing System Design

The implementation of a sustained, pan-Arctic observing system can be considered as a hierarchy of sub-problems (Fig. 1). However, since implementation has progressed and continues to evolve at all levels of this hierarchy, questions of observing system design cannot be addressed in isolation (bottom-up or top-down) but need to be considered in the context of existing efforts. This process is naturally challenging but it allows continuation of the implementation of an increasingly complex and optimized observing system. Significant benefits can be derived from the synergistic implementation of different studies, initiatives and programs already underway.

One promising strategy to draw on such benefits is to anchor the design and planning of the observing system in the context of the hierarchy shown in Fig. 1. The scientific drivers of an observing system are well established and already guide the implementation of individual projects as well as that of the integrated system. The linkages between individual projects in the context of overarching trans-disciplinary programs such as SEARCH or ISAC is emerging but presently not fully developed. Similarly, there are emerging benefits from international coordination and implementation although this process is still in an exploratory stage (e.g., SEARCH for DAMOCLES).

It should be emphasized that although lacking a theoretically based approach, observing system design is already actively underway on a scientifically informed basis. For example, individual projects use information on the dynamics of the system including spatial and temporal scales of movement of air, water and ice for system design. They also make use of existing data sets by artificially reducing the data density in sections until some of the prominent features can no longer be resolved. Terrestrial observations utilize information on typical vegetation migration rates from modern or paleo-observations to design an observing program that would capture future northward migration of specific species. Modeling studies are increasingly analyzed for information on critical time scales, particle tracking to simulate Lagrangian experiments, or Eulerian type time series sampling to infer expected frequencies and amplitudes of perturbations at fixed points. These empirical designs are becoming more sophisticated as the data sets increase and the models are able to more realistically simulate processes in nature. Analysis of services provided by components of the Arctic system and institutional analysis are being employed to help organize stakeholder information needs that inform an observing system.

Most of the methods described above are applied to design observing activities on the scale that can be handled by single PI's or by PI groups. The design of system-scale, single-domain observing systems is still lagging the design of individual, geographically limited components, in terms of sophistication and optimization. Even more work has to be done to optimize observing system components that cross domains although these are exactly the type of observing systems that are needed for modern, theme-driven, system-based studies. Tackling these tasks has to be given immediate attention and high priority for effective observing system design and implementation.

Steps towards Improvement of Observing System Design

The following objectives can guide us towards improvement of observing system design:

- (a) evaluate the current implementation status of the Arctic Observing System;
- (b) improve design and adaptation of observing system components through observing system simulation experiments and similar approaches;
- (c) synthesize information arriving from the existing observing system components and quantitative design studies to guide its design and refinement;
- (d) coordinate between individual national and international efforts. Here, ISAC can help with international aspects of coordination.

A process that would advance these goals might include the following tasks:

(1) Assessment of the present state and near-term implementation plans of the AON and related efforts

SEARCH mainly through members of its SSC, OCP, and UCP, with a few key contributors from ARCSS and the broader Arctic community will prepare an assessment of the AON in its current form. This review will examine how well the existing system addresses the major Arctic Change science questions, identify critical gaps and make recommendations for the next steps in the integration of observing system efforts. A starting point for this activity would be the Report from the 2008 Arctic Observations Integration Workshop (<http://www.arcus.org/search/meetings/2008/aow/report.php>) which contains both a mix of very specific and very broad recommendations. Some of these need to be revisited, but significant guidance can be derived from the Workshops 10 short-term recommendations. Based on communication with the UCP, this activity would point to critical needs that can then be used to guide further build-up of the AON in areas where the benefits are most immediate and substantial for understanding arctic change. The timing of this activity would be preferably such that results are available as input to activities #3 and #5 below.

(2) Exploring and as appropriate applying a variety of tools for observing system design and optimization

Lacking the comprehensive theoretical framework for observing system design and optimization requires the application of all available methods that provide information on the performance and options for future enhancement of the observing system. These

methods include observing system simulation experiments (OSSE), evaluation of the information coming from the the data assimilation community (e.g., reanalysis and forecasting projects) or tools such as manipulation of data sets to examine the data density required to capture the processes that determine the characteristic features of the observed system components. This process needs coordination, an interface with the AON data management system (CADIS or equivalent) and the involvement of the modeling community.

To initiate this process, it is proposed to convene a group of experts representing the Arctic change community (incl. one or two participants outside of the Arctic research community), members from the SEARCH SSC, OCP and UCP, and the ARCSS committee representing the broader Arctic scientific community interests, and a few other key contributors. The latter will comprise experts on observing system design familiar with a broad range of approaches, including methods other than OSSEs. This group will also include a few key individuals that can ensure that discussion of observing system design is addressing the question of how to respond to change, a key component of the SEARCH program and a recognized challenge for stakeholder in the Arctic and lower latitudes.

After constitution of this group, a workshop in Fall 2009 would lay out a strategy for choosing the most promising approaches and methods for Arctic observing system design and optimization. The group would define a set of specific tasks, such as proof-of-concept activities, that would be assigned to individual PI's or small PI groups and would be supported at the appropriate level. These tasks would have to be performed in a short period of time so that their results could inform the immediate next steps in the development the Arctic observing system. These results would inform a second workshop in spring 2010 that would evaluate these and other efforts and summarize findings and resulting recommendations into a report that would form the foundation for further future efforts (such as future calls for proposals, coordination of activities etc.). The report should in particular provide guidance to NSF on the design, implementation and longer-term perspective of an Arctic observing system. The observing system design would not only be informed by data from instrumental records and models, but would also utilize paleo-data to place the present changes into the proper historical context and strengthen the attribution studies.

Finally, in order to have these activities tie into efforts at the national and international level, avoid duplication and maintain continuity, it is critical to have strong involvement by the SEARCH Project Office, possibly with some more direct involvement from the ISAC Program Office where international coordination is concerned.

(3) Synthesis and discussion of design options and approaches as part of the AON PI Meeting, fall 2009

The AON PI Meeting offers an opportunity to synthesize ongoing activities reported at the level of themes or disciplines rather than individual projects, with invitees from within and outside of SEARCH to provide such broader-scale evaluations. The

participation of AON PIs who have spent significant time and effort on the (mostly) disciplinary and region-specific aspects of an AON would allow for productive discussion of these synthesis talks. Participating members from the AON program, the SEARCH Observing Change and Understanding Change Panels (OCP, UCP), and the SEARCH SSC would provide perspectives on system design approaches in the context of SEARCH. Agency personnel involved in observation programs, such as the Dept. of Interior's Regional Climate Monitoring Network design team, could provide input on interagency coordination aspects where needed. Furthermore, experts with a perspective on the international observing system landscape (e.g., DAMOCLES, ArcticNet and Asian programs) would provide input on pan-Arctic coordination. This could potentially take the form of a full day devoted to international coordination, organized, e.g., by ISAC.

Broader questions on options and approaches in the design of an observing system would be addressed by a few contributions that could report on ongoing efforts in other programs, e.g., the the ARGO program, the global repeat hydrography program, the TAO array, basin-wide hydrology programs (e.g. in the Southwest?), or the Arctic Sea Ice Outlook as a synthesis effort with strong potential to guide observing system design.

(4) Interagency coordination

Following the AON Meeting, which would encourage attendance from agency personnel, a small group of participants would communicate with agency representatives, including a higher administrative levels, to provide a brief report and discuss the next steps of observing network implementation. One key need would be to identify agency personnel who would be tasked with contributing to the planning and implementation effort, and here the Interagency Program Management Committee (IPMC) can be of help. Another option would be to dedicate an IARPC Principals meeting to the topic of AON design and implementation.

(5) White paper on Arctic observing system design

A more fundamental examination of the design philosophies, options and challenges for a comprehensive AON may require the form of a white paper that draws on, but goes well beyond efforts currently underway at the disciplinary or project-level (Fig. 1). The group working on such a white paper would comprise a balanced mix of Arctic experts drawn from the SEARCH SSC and panels, the ARCSS program, and others in combination with key contributors outside of the polar community. The paper would address in particular those aspects unique to the AON and try to map out the fundamental aspects of a design and implementation strategy that successfully addresses the challenges outlined above. This white paper would be written by the groups attending the two workshops and vetted within the broader community.

(6) Guidance on societal information needs: Responding to Change

A key aspect of the SEARCH program is the integration of activities that address the observation, understanding and response to Arctic environmental change. Hence,

guidance on the societal information needs component of an observing system will be critical at all steps of the way. In order to help with this task, key experts will have to be part of the different activities outlined above. At a later stage, this will include involvement of the Responding to Change Panel (RCP) in order to help address how to best integrate activities directed at registration, adaptation and mitigation of Arctic change. Since RCP encompasses much more than guidance on information needs (incl. dedicated acquisition and analyses of socio-economic data sets) further thought may have to go towards the bridging of responding to change activities to the AON. Here, close collaboration with groups subsumed under ISAC may be of help.

Timeline of activities

- June 2009: UCP, working with SSC, OCP and ARCSS to identify a group of people (beyond UCP and key OCP members) that would initiate planning for a review of present state and near-term implementation plans of the AON in the context of SEARCH and ISAC science questions, SSC, OCP, and UCP develops charge for this task (John Walsh, Hajo Eicken, Peter Schlosser)
- June: OCP (with others) begins planning for Observing System implementation workshop convened after AON PI meeting
- June: identify a group of people to constitute an AON Design and Implementation Working Group (ADI WG) to evaluate efforts such as OSSEs to help guide AON design and implementation (Hajo Eicken, John Walsh, Peter Schlosser in consultation with SEARCH SSC, ARCSS Committee and NSF-OPP)
- July-September: organize a small group of people to work on white paper that address broader-scale challenges and potential paths in an integrated, evolving Arctic Observing System
- July-September: ADI WG meets electronically and through teleconference to plan activities and fall workshop
- August/September: Report from UCP et al. on AON evaluation/status is due
- Summer/Fall: IARPC principals meeting to discuss interagency coordination with SEARCH attendance
- October: Combination of implementation meetings (ADI WG Workshop, International Coordination Meeting) centered around AON PI meeting
- November 2009 – April 2010: ADI WG and other scientists continues work on specific tasks defined during the first workshop
- May 2010: Second ADI WG workshop with 1st draft of report on implementation and design planning that integrates 1st workshop report, white paper and other input from the broader community
- June 2010: Final report on ADI WG activities

Figure 1: Schematic of a hierarchy of approaches and activities governing design and implementation of an Arctic observing system.

Appendix 4. State of the Arctic Organizing Committee (as of 1 July 2009)				
State of the Arctic Conference 2010				
Organizing Committee (Internal Document, Updated 1 July 09)				
Name	Role/Organization	Expertise/Affiliation	Website	Email
Executive Committee				
Peter Schlosser, SEARCH SSC Chair	SEARCH SSC Chair; Lamont-Doherty	Oceanography	http://www.ldeo.columbia.edu/~etg/text/peters.html	schlosser@ldeo.columbia.edu
Martin Fortier	ArcticNet Executive Director, Universite Laval	Oceanography	http://www.arcticnet.ulaval.ca/index.php?fa=ArcticNet.aboutUs&home=14&person_id=100	Martin.Fortier@arcticnet.ulaval.ca
Jean-Claude Gascard (add to Executive Committee)	DAMOCLES Chair; Universite Pierre et Marie Curie	Oceanography	http://www.damocles-eu.org/	jga@lodyc.jussieu.fr
Maribeth Murray	International Study of Arctic Change (ISAC) Executive Director; UAF	Anthropology, human dimensions	http://www.uaf.edu/anthro/FacultyPages/MSM.html	ffmsm@uaf.edu
Josh Schimel, AC Chair	ARCSS Committee Chair; UC Santa Barbara	Soil ecology, biochemistry	http://www.lifesci.ucsb.edu/eemb/faculty/schimel/	Schimel@lifesci.ucsb.edu
Helen Wiggins	ARCUS, Director of Programs	Science planning, (forest ecology)	www.arcus.org	helen@arcus.org
Other OC Members				
Michael Tjernstrom	ISAC Science Steering Group Co-Chair; Stockholm University	Meteorology	http://www.misu.su.se/~michaelt/peop_michael.html	michaelt@misu.su.se
Koji Shimada	Japan Agency for Marine-Earth Science and Technology (JAMSTEC)	Ocean/climate System	*no webpage linked specifically to Koji	shimadak@jamstec.go.jp
Hajo Eicken	Geophysical Institute UAF; SEARCH Observing Change Panel Chair	Sea ice geophysics, seasonal arctic ice zones	http://www.gi.alaska.edu/snowice/sea-lake-ice/eicken.html	hajo.eicken@gi.alaska.edu
Craig Fleener	Director of Subsistence Division, AK Dept. of Fish & Game, SEARCH OCP member	Arctic communities, subsistence, resource management,	http://www.adfg.state.ak.us/news/2008/10-14-08_nr.php (gives good overview)	craig.fleener@alaska.gov
(Robert) Max Holmes	Woods Hole Research Center, SEARCH SSC	Arctic global climate change, arctic hydrologic cycle, education/outreach	http://www.whrc.org/about_us/whos_who/CV/rholmes.htm	rholmes@whrc.org
Bruce Forbes	Arctic Center, Univ. of Lapland	Applied ecology & geography in permafrost environments, management of arctic ungulates	http://www.arcticcentre.org/?deptid=8817	bforbes@ulapland.fi
Amy Tidwell	IPY Postdoc Research Fellow, UAF Water & Environmental Research Fellow	Climate change impact assessments for water resources, water resources management	http://www.uaf.edu/water/PostDocs/Tidwell/	fnact@uaf.edu
Andi (Andrea) Lloyd	Dept. of Biology, Middlebury College	Global change biology, plant community biology, productivity of arctic woody vegetation in warming climate	http://community.middlebury.edu/~lloyd/index.html	lloyd@middlebury.edu
Elena Andreeva	Institute for System Analysis, Russian Academy of Sciences	Climate change, cryosphere, complex systems	http://www.ras.ru/win/db/show_per.asp?P=.id-4316.In-en	vnisi@isa.ru
Jinping Zhao	Ocean University of China	Global ocean change	University website: http://www.ouc.edu.cn/english/aboutouc/aboutouc.html	jpzhaou@ouc.edu.cn
Tentative:				
Duane Smith	President & Vice-Chair Inuit Circumpolar Council (Canada)	Inuit People, renewable resource use & management,	inac.gc.ca/ai/mr/nr/s-d2005/02709bkd-eng.asp (bottom of page)	inuvialuk@northwestern.net
<i>Declined:</i>				
Richard Alley	<i>Evan Pugh Professor of Geosciences, Penn State</i>	<i>Glaciology, ice sheet stability, paleoclimates from ice cores, abrupt climate change</i>	http://www.geosc.psu.edu/people/faculty/personalpages/ralley/	ralley@essc.psc.edu